

TOMATO PRODUCTION UNDER LOW-COST PLASTIC HOUSE: A PRACTICAL GUIDE FOR SMALLHOLDER FARMERS IN ETHIOPIA

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1. INTRODUCTION

Common Name: Tomato

Scientific name: *Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.

Local name: ተግተግ (Amharic)

Tomato is one of the most important vegetables grown in Ethiopia. The crop is grown as cash crop mostly by smallholder farmers throughout the country. In Ethiopia, tomato is mainly produced under irrigation production system during the off-season. The production of tomato during the rainy season is not common, which is associated by biotic and abiotic diseases. The market supply of tomatoes from July to November is therefore low that escalates the price of tomatoes to the unaffordable high level. Although tomatoes can be produced during the rainy season in low humid areas of the country, it is associated with the intensive use of fungicides and insecticides, which incur high cost of production and environmental pollutions.

Low-cost plastic house is an innovative solution for the production of warm season vegetables like tomatoes during the rainy season by protecting the crops from excessive rainfall and associated diseases and insect, harsh weather conditions, increasing yield and quality. The technology helps to grow tomatoes throughout the year. The tomatoes grown in protected structures like low-cost plastic house fetch higher prices in the market and help to improve the incomes of smallholder farmers. Low-cost plastic house can be constructed using locally available materials (plastic sheet, wood, cement, rubber string, etc.). The technology is employed in various developing countries for the production of tomatoes during the rainy season. This production guideline is therefore developed for smallholder- tomato growers with the purpose of describing the principles and procedures of tomato production under low-cost plastic house.

2. CLIMATIC AND SOIL REQUIREMENTS

Although tomato is fairly adaptable to different agro-ecologies, it prefers warm conditions with optimum temperatures ranging from 15 °C to 25 °C. Tomato is sensitive to frost and tolerant to high temperature especially during flowering. Tomato seed germination is best at temperature around 29 °C. Normally, flowering does not occur below 15 °C or above 35 °C. Temperatures above 30 °C inhibit fruit set, lycopene development and flavor.

Tomato grows well in a wide range of soils, provided the soil contains good and deeply worked organic matter. Well-drained soils with a pH range of 5 - 7.5 are suitable for tomato production. Generally soils heavier than sandy or sandy-loam are better for higher yield. In case of heavy soils, drainage is critical in tomato production. Soil analysis should be done before fertilizer application.

3. CHOICE OF VARIETY AND SEEDLING PRODUCTION

3.1. Choice of tomato variety

The choice of adaptive and high yielder variety is very critical for good yields and successful production of tomatoes. The choice of varieties is based on availability and adaptability to the growing conditions, fruit quality, resistance/tolerance to diseases and insect pests, quality (firmness), plant growth habit, and preference of the specific market, and the planting time. Farmers need to choose those varieties that will meet the needs and are suited to the growing climate.

According to their growth habits, tomatoes are indeterminate and determinate. Indeterminate varieties produce new shoots continuously, inflorescence occurs on every third or fourth leaf, and fruits mature sequentially (Fig. 1, left). These varieties are preferred for protected production system including low-cost plastic house and they need staking for supporting the plants. In case of determinate, shoot development is terminated after four to six inflorescences (Fig. 1, right). These groups of tomato varieties are short and bush and in most cases they are preferred for open field production. These types of tomatoes ripen early, are easier to harvest and have a more concentrated fruit maturity. Mostly they do not need supports. However staking of plants decreases the incidence of diseases caused due to suffocation.

Fig. 1: Indeterminate (left) and determinate (right) growth habit of tomatoes

Source: Ethio-SHEP, (2019)

In Ethiopia, different open-pollinated varieties of tomatoes (Table 1) are grown by smallholder farmers that are released by the Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR) and Regional Agricultural Research Institutes. Recently, however, farmers are started to grow hybrid tomato varieties where their seeds are supplied by different seed companies in Ethiopia. Hybrids are often high yielder and their seeds cannot be harvested and saved for future planting. Hybrid seeds are usually more expensive than inbred/ open-pollinated. Hybrid tomato varieties are preferred for greenhouse production including low-cost plastic house.

Table 1: Selected tomato varieties grown by farmers in Ethiopia

Variety	Growth type	Growth period after transplanting	Yield (t/ha)	Remark
Melkashola	Determinate	100-120	43	Open pollinated
Melkasalssa	Determinate	100-120	45	Open pollinated
Roma VF	Determinate	95-100	40	Open pollinated
Galilama	Determinate	80-92	50	Open pollinated
Galilea	Semi-determinate	60-90	69.5	Hybrid
Galilea-39				Hybrid
Shanty	Semi-determinate	60-90	69.7	Hybrid
Eden F1	Determinate	75	59.9	Hybrid
Anna F1	Determinate	75	54.3	Hybrid
Gabbi	Determinate			Hybrid

3.2. Tomato Seedling Production

Tomato seedlings can be either purchased from certified nursery enterprise or produced by the farmers in their own nursery. In case of self-production, it is advised to produce seedlings on raised based using certified seeds purchased from seed companies. About 250 g of seed which has approximately 70,000 seeds are required to cover one hectare of land. Seeds that are purchased from the reputable seed companies are usually treated with broad spectrum fungicides such as Captan, Lindane, Carbosulfan, Tebuconazole, Imidacloprid or Tolclofos methyl Triazoxide to control damping off. It is possible to raise tomato seedlings on nursery soil or in plastic seeding trays.

3.2.1. Seedling production in nursery seedbed

Nursery seedbed method is the common seedling production system mostly practiced by smallholder farmers in Ethiopia. It is advisable to use a nursery site that is well-drained and not previously planted with a Solanaceous crop. Seedbeds are mostly raised about 15-20 cm above the ground level for draining the excess water. The top soil of the seedbed should be mixed with well-decomposed manure or compost for enhancing the water holding capacity.

If it is possible, it is advised to sterilize the soil with solar energy (solarization) or chemicals. Sterilization helps to kill eggs and larvae of insect pests and pathogens as well as weed seeds. It prevents the seedlings from damping-off and other soil-borne diseases. The best time for

solarization is during the dry season with high temperatures. Follow the procedures described below for efficient solarization of seedbed.

Procedures of solarization (Fig. 2):

1. Plow the soil and prepare the seedbed
2. Apply water to moist the seedbed soil
3. Cover the moist soil with transparent plastic sheets for 3-4 weeks (bury the edges of the sheets in the soil)
4. After 3-4 weeks, remove the plastic sheets
5. About 2-3 days later, level the soil and sow the seeds

Fig. 2: Raised seedbeds and solarization
Source: Lin et al. (2015)

Sowing: Sow the seeds evenly in rows of 5 cm apart and 0.5 cm deep at a rate of 750–900 seeds/m². Cover the seeds in the rows lightly using either soil from the bed or finely sieved compost. Mulch the seeded bed with mulching materials

Watering: Water the seedbed daily during the hot and dry season by using watering cane to maintain optimum moisture for healthy seedling growth. In the cool season, watering once in every two days may be enough. While watering, avoid excess water application.

Thinning: Remove the mulch soon after the seedlings emerge. Allow seedlings to grow about 5 cm apart within the row. Thin out the excess plants. This is usually done within 2-3 days after the first true leaf has appeared (about 5-7 days after sowing). Excess seedlings can be transplanted to trays or individual containers for transplanting to the field later, especially when expensive seeds such as hybrid varieties are used.

3.2.2. Growing seedlings in container

This method involves raising seedlings in separate pots/containers or plastic/plug trays to provide adequate nutrients and growing medium for healthy root development and seedling growth. Seedlings rose in individual containers or plug trays normally have a 100%

establishment rate in the field since they are transplanted with the medium-root block (Fig. 3, red circle). This prevents injury to the roots and transplanting shock to the seedlings.

Fig. 3: *Tomato seedlings grown in pots or plug cells*

Source: Lin et al. (2015)

Seedling container: Containers made of different materials like paper, perforated plastic bags (5-7 cm wide and 10 cm long), thin plastic pots 5-7 cm in diameter or commercial plastic/Styrofoam plug trays can be used for tomato seedling production (Fig. 4). All containers, pots or cells must have a hole in the base for draining excess water. Containers should be fully cleaned and exposed to sunlight or disinfected with 1% solution of chlorine bleach before and after use.

Fig. 4: Containers for raising tomato seedlings: plastic plug trays (top, left & right), plastic pots (bottom, left) or plastic bags (bottom, right)

Source: Lin et al. (2015)

Growing medium: Fill the containers or plug trays with a medium that drains well, such as commercial potting media (cocopeat, peat, moss or a mixture of sand and compost). If commercial potting media is not available fill the container with a mixture of locally available materials such as forest soil, sand, well-decomposed compost in 3:2:1 ratio.

Medium sterilization: The medium should be steamed at 120 °C for 45 minutes, or watered and heat-sterilized in covered soil sterilizers for 6-12 hours, or sterilized through solarization for 3-4 weeks to minimize levels of soil-borne pathogens, nematodes and insect pests. Please refer soil sterilization procedures under Section 3.2.1 above.

Sowing, watering and thinning in container seedling production: Sow 2 seeds per pot or cell and cover the seeds with fine compost or potting mixture, and water gently with a fine watering can. Place the pots or plug trays on top of bricks or benches in a net tunnel or net house. Thin out the excess seedlings and keep only one seedling per pot/cell when the seedlings attained 1-2 true leaves (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Covering the seeds with potting mixture (top, left) or fine compost (top, right); watering with fine can (bottom, left); keeping only one seedling per cell after thinning (bottom, right)

Source: Lin et al. (2015)

3.2.3. Seedling management in nursery

In addition to watering, thinning and mulching, disease and insect pest control and fertilization are the major management activities in tomato seedling production in nursery. Damping-off is the major diseases of vegetable seedlings in nursery including tomatoes. It is caused by different fungi that live in the soil (*Pythium*, *Rhizoctonia*, and *Phytophthora spp.*) They occur in damp wet soils. Young seedlings develop a sunken, brown, necrotic lesion near the soil line. The lesion girdles the stem leading the collapse and death of the seedlings (Fig. 6).

Management of Damping-off

- Avoiding over watering of the seedlings
- Ensuring proper seedling spacing for aeration
- Using healthy, disease-free and vigorous seedlings
- Disinfecting the seedbeds before sowing the seeds.

Fig.6: Necrotic and brown lesion the stem base and collapse of seedling (red circle) due to Damping-off

Source: Lin et al. (2015)

Fertilization

Application of fertilizer depends on the status of soil fertility. Supply of nitrogen to the growing medium can help producing healthy and vigorous seedlings. If the seedlings are thin or the leaves turn a pale yellow-green color, especially on the older leaves foliage (Fig. 10 left red circled), it is advised to apply 0.25% urea solution (2.5 g urea dissolved in 1 liter of water) 7-10 days after thinning. The second application could be secluded one day before transplanting. However, avoid excess nitrogen application as it may lead to thin and tall seedlings (Fig. 7 right picture, left plant). Generally, it is recommended to monitor the seedlings growth daily. If the seedlings grow too rapidly before transplanting, apply less fertilizer.

Fig. 7: Seedlings with pale yellow-green leaves that require nitrogen (left, red circle); thin and tall plants due to excessive nitrogen or weak sunlight (right picture, left plant); stocky, strong and sturdy seedling (right picture, right plant)

Source: Lin et al. (2015)

4. CONSTRUCTION OF LOW-COST PLASTIC HOUSE

Low-cost house can be constructed using locally available building materials like wood, nail, cement, etc. and covered with white transparent plastic sheets (10 micrometer thickness). The covering polyethylene sheet should be UV resistant and have transparency percentage of 90-95%, allowing ample sunlight to enter the house for plant growth while still providing some shade and protection. The construction site should be free of shade trees grown around the house as the shade influence the growth, yield and quality of tomatoes. It should be constructed in areas with enough sunlight and aeration. Keeping the wind direction is also necessary to reduce damages of the plastic house.

The size of the low-cost plastic house depends on the availability of land for construction and the financial capacity of the farmers. The size influences the cost of investment, the quantity of production, cost of production and the net benefit of the farm. Therefore, it is wise to construct the minimum size of the house that brings sizeable net benefit. In the research conducted by Abebu (2024), low-cost plastic house (7 m x 20 m = 140 m²) constructed on each of four farmer`s land was financially feasible and profitable. The plastic house should have a height of at least 4.0 m at the center while the side can be about 2.5 m high to prevent heat stress and facilitate aeration during the day time.

It is necessary have side vents in both sides of the house for efficient ventilation and moisture control where the side vents are covered by insect proof net to control the entrance of insect in to the house. To prevent the blow away of the plastic sheet, it is also necessary to draw rubber string over the plastic from one side to the other and fix it with nail (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Low-cost plastic house constructed from locally available materials

5. ESTABLISHMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF TOMATOES UNDER LOW-COST PLASTIC HOUSE

5.1 Soil Preparation and Seedling Transplanting

Soils in low-cost plastic house can be worked out by using hand digging tools (Fig. 9, left). During digging hardpans or compacted soil should be thoroughly loosened to enable the root system to spread to a depth of 40 – 60 cm. Application of well-decomposed compost is necessary to enhance the water holding capacity, fertility and structure of the soil. If the soil has low pH, addition of lime (CaCO_3) increase the soil pH while application of Gypsum (CaSO_4) reduces the pH in basic or sodic soils. After digging, level the land and prepare raised bed about 20 cm above the ground level.

Tomato seedlings grown in nursery are ready for transplanting when they reached at 3-5 leaf stage with the approximate height of 15-25 cm. Watering the seedlings about 12-14 hours

before the date of transplanting is necessary to reduce the root damages while uprooting. This is especially important if seedlings are grown in nursery soil. Transplanting is done at the spacing of 100 cm between rows and 50 cm between plants (Fig. 9, right). While transplanting select healthy and strong seedlings, which have at least 3-5 true leaves (about 4 weeks old), around 12-25 cm in length, short internode length, vigorous and stock no insect pest and disease symptoms (Fig. 10). An empty space of 0.75 – 1.0 m is necessary between the rows of tomato plants to facilitate the agronomic practices including cultivation, fertilizer application, watering and harvesting. It is advised to transplant tomato seedling late in the afternoon or at cloudy days to minimize transplanting shock. While planting insert the seedlings in a hole in such a way that the first true leaves are 5 – 10 cm above the ground surface. Press the soil firmly around the root and water around the base of the plant. Application of water soon after transplanting is quit necessary to enhance the establishment of seedling in the production field.

Fig. 9: Soil preparation (left) and transplanted tomato seedlings (right)

Fig. 10: Healthy and vigorous tomato seedlings raised in pots (left) and plastic plug trays (right) that are ready for transplanting

5.2 Watering

Water is essential for plants including for tomatoes. Especially in protected production system, application of water is necessary to reduce water stress and associated reduction of growth and development of tomato plants. Irrigation is especially necessary during critical periods like flower setting and growth of the fruits. Regular watering reduces physiological disorder like blossom end rot, sun scorch and fruit splitting and ensures uniform fruit development, enhances fruit growth and increases the size and number of fruits. On the other hand excess water increases water logging leading to Magnesium, Phosphorous and Nitrogen deficiencies and diseases.

Water is applied preferably using drip irrigation. However, due to its high initial cost, smallholder farmers can use watering can and apply water on the soil at the base of the plants (Fig. 11). It is necessary to avoid the contact of irrigation water with the aboveground parts such as leaves, fruits and stem of the plants. Watering the aboveground parts of the plants enhances the development of diseases.

The frequency and quantity of water depends on the environmental conditions and the growth stage of tomato plants. It is advised to irrigate tomato seedlings daily early in the morning until the seedlings fully established. Then after, watering is done in three days interval until flowering. After flowering, watering at five days interval is enough, which depends on the environmental conditions.

Fig. 11: Water application at the base of the plants (blue circle)

5.3 Nutrient Management

Tomato requires fertile soil, especially high level of organic matter. Fertilizer application is therefore required. The amount of fertilizer depends on the soil fertility, the environmental conditions and the yielding potential of the variety. The amount of nutrients in the soil can be estimated by a laboratory soil test. However, farmer`s level soil analysis is difficult in developing country like Ethiopia. Therefore, in soils of poor in organic matter apply about 20 t ha⁻¹ (two handfuls per planting hole) of well-decomposed manure and mix it thoroughly with the soil during the land preparation. In addition, apply NPS fertilizer at the rate of 242 kg ha⁻¹ (which is equivalent to 10 g or one teaspoonful per planting hole) and mix it well with soil at the time of planting.

Apply urea at the rate of 200 kg ha⁻¹ in split application. Apply the first half (5g or ½ teaspoonful per plant) as top-dressing after the establishment of the seedlings (25 cm height) and the remaining half (5g or ½ teaspoonful per plant) 35-40 days after transplanting. Inadequate nutrient levels may result in deficiency disorders that can be observed as patterns of leaf discoloration or fruit abnormality. The major nutritional disorder in tomato is blossom end rot caused by calcium deficiency. Other common nutrient disorder symptoms include chlorosis of older leaves due to nitrogen deficiency, stunted growth, purpling of leaves and late fruit maturation due to inadequate phosphorus and drying of leaf margins coupled with

hollow fruit when potassium is limiting. Deficiency disorders can be corrected by application of foliar fertilizers.

5.4 Training/Staking

Staking is the process of supporting tomato plant, which especially necessary in protected cultivation including low-cost plastic house. It improves fruit quality by keeping plants and fruits off the ground and by providing better spray coverage. It also helps better air circulation around the plant and reduces the incidence of diseases and insect pests in the house. It is also easier to harvest staked tomatoes than tomatoes growing across the ground. Staking is started after 25 to 30 days after transplanting. It is done by fixing bamboo or wooden poles between the rows in the ridges at certain interval (2-3 m). These wooden poles are then connected horizontally at a uniform height using metal wires or wood. Each plant is then tied vertically with the horizontal metal wire or wood using thread (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12: Staked tomato plants grown in low-cost plastic house

5.5 Cultivation/Weeding

Hoeing is an important operation in tomato production and helps managing weeds that compete for growth factors like light, water, and nutrients. Weeding also helps to destroy alternate hosts of insect pests and diseases that may attack tomatoes. Cultivation/hoeing loosen the soil surface around plants for good aeration. It is done when the soil is moist, but not wet.

5.6 Pruning

Pruning is selective removal of side shoots (suckers) of tomatoes to limit plant growth, which is especially necessary in protected cultivation. Pruning helps maintaining the balance between vegetative and reproductive growth. Pruning can cause fruit to mature earlier and grow to greater size and uniformity. Pruning improves air circulation within the canopy, which reduces foliar diseases, and facilitates spraying and harvesting. Indeterminate tomato varieties grown in greenhouse should be always pruned so that they do not produce too much vegetative growth. Indeterminate tomato plants without pruning will produce excessive vegetative growth with reduced fruit size. Indeterminate tomatoes are commonly produced as two or three main stem crop and the other lateral branches that appear in the leaf axils are pinched out. It is advised to pinch out suckers with figure at their early growth to avoid damages on tomato plants (Fig. 13). After 4-6 ties on the stake pinch out the growing tip to enhance the fruit size. Removing the leaves close to the ground helps prevent the entry of blight.

Fig. 13: Side shoots/suckers on tomato plants that should be pinchout by fingur

Sanitation is critical while pruning the branches. Pruning shares should be sharp and clean. They should be cleaned with alcohol or any other disinfectant. Smokers should wash their hands before handling plants as they may otherwise spread tobacco virus disease. It has been

reported that pruning reduces early and total yield, detrimentally affects quality and increases the incidence of viral diseases and other disorders.

5.7 Insect Pests, Diseases and their Management

Tomato is attacked by the wide ranges of insect pests and diseases both in open field and protected production systems. In addition, tomatoes are liable to physiological disorders that are caused by adverse environmental conditions and nutrient deficiencies during growth and development, storage and marketing. For successful production, tomato pests should be managed by the integration of different management options including cultural, mechanical, physical, chemical and biological methods.

Major diseases, insect pests and physiological disorders that commonly attacked tomatoes under protected structure in Ethiopian conditions are described below. The symptoms and possible management options of these pests are also presented below in Table 2.

Table 2: Major diseases and insect pests of tomatoes under protected production in Ethiopia

I. Common insect pests of tomatoes				
Name	Description	Damages/symptoms	Damage/symptom picture	Management options
1. Cutworms	Larvae found in the soil cut the seedlings at the ground level. During day time it hides in the soil feed on the roots and during night it feeds on the areal part. Infestation is more common in weedy spots	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cut the seedlings stem at the soil line and damages the roots • Plants with damaged roots will wilt and die. 	<p><i>Cutworm damages</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control weeds at least two weeks prior to planting • Slightly dig the soil around the plant and remove it by hand. • Apply 5% Malathion dust around the plant after transplanting • Spray Sevin, Fastac or Karate insecticides
2. Leaf miners	The larvae feed by mining between the upper and lower epidermis of the leaves. Occasionally the larvae can be seen within the leaf mine as it feeds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mining of the epidermis that causes whitish blotches of the leaves • Mining kills the leaves and causes leaf fall. • Damages allow the fungal diseases to enter in to the leaves, (secondary infection). 	<p><i>Leaf miner damaged tomato leaf</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use yellow sticky traps or yellow basins filled with water that attracts the adult leaf miner. • Destroy old crop debris • Crop rotation • Use of pesticides (pesticide rotation is advised)

<p>3. White fly (<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>)</p>	<p>Small mealy insects with two pairs of white wings. Adult found on the underside of the leaves. The insect transmits viral diseases</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • White fly sucks leaf sap and removes nutrients which cause yellowing • The larvae secrete honey dew which supports growth of black sooty mold 	<p>White fly on underside of the leaf</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weed control • Using yellow sticky traps • Using Karate 2.5WG®, Diazinon or Brigade
<p>4. Tomato fruit borer/Fruit worm</p>	<p>Young caterpillars have prominent rows of dark bumps on back while older caterpillars are dark gray to light brown and have lengthwise stripes on the body.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Young larvae feed on the tender leaves while the matured larvae bore into the fruit and eat the inner contents • The larvae push only a part of its body into the fruit. 	<p>Fruit damage by tomato fruit borer</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using pheromone trap and light trap with water pan to trap and destroy the adult • Planting sunflower at border to collect and destroy egg masses and young larvae • Using insecticide before entering the fruit
<p>II. Common diseases of tomatoes</p>				
<p>1. Powdery Mildew</p>	<p>The disease starts on the upper side and spreads to lower leaf surface. High temperature and relative humidity favor the infection. Older plants are more susceptible</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • White talcum-like coatings on the leaves • Leaf surface develops yellow patches which will die later on • Weak plants • Leaf death favors sun burning of fruits 	<p>Powdery mildew on tomato leaves</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Removing and destroying crop debris after harvest. • Weed control • Practice crop rotation • Spray Redomil gold MZ 68WG and mancozeb fungicides

<p>2. Late blight</p>	<p>Caused by the fungus <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (Mont.) de Bary. Occurs when there is continuous heavy dew for 2 or more days followed by cloudy weather condition. It infects most parts of the plants (leaf, stem, fruit)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water-soaked lesions that enlarge to brown lesion on the entire leaf • In cool conditions, gray/white moldy growth occurs on the underside of the lesions. • Infected leaves shrivel, die and dry up. • Infected stems appear brown to black 	<p>Brown lesions on leaves and stem (top) and fruit (bottom)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow an integrated approach: sanitary measures, resistant varieties, and well-timed chemical sprays • Crop rotation • Using resistant or tolerant varieties • Keep proper aeration (optimum spacing, ventilation and staking) • Destroy infected parts of plants • Spray protective (Mancozeb) and curative (Ridomil) fungicides
<p>3. Fusarium wilt</p>	<p>It is caused by <i>Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. lycopersici</i>. The pathogen is disseminated by seed and soil. The disease is more prevalent in warm (25 – 32 °C) and acidic (pH 5.0-5.6) sandy soils.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yellowing of leaflets on one side of the leaf • Yellowed leaves may die and drop off. • Browning of the vascular system that restricts the movement of water and nutrients • Stunted growth of infected plants 	<p>Yellowing of leaflet (left) and browning of vascular system (right)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply lime to increase the soil pH (pH 7.0) • Crop rotation • Removing debris and crop residues • Weed control • Staking plants to improve aeration and to prevent the contact of plants with the soil • Using Fusarium resistant tomato

				varieties
4. Bacterial wilt	It is one of the most economic diseases of tomatoes and potatoes. It is caused by <i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i> . The disease is mainly seed borne in tomatoes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapid wilt of the plants and buildup of adventitious roots on the infected stem. It causes browning of the vascular bundles. The infected stem (xylem) in water releases a slimy stream of whitish bacterial cells. 	<p>Wilting of plants (left) and browning of vascular system (right)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice long term crop rotation with non- Solanaceous crops • Produce transplants in pathogen free soil. • Remove and burn infected plants as soon as possible • If possible, use resistant tomato cultivars
5. Root-knot nematodes (<i>Meloidogyne Spp.</i>)	They live in soil and attack roots. They are promoted by sandy soils and warm temperatures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stunting, wilting, and yellowing of leaves that leads to plant death. • Roots develop large knots (galls) that restrict the transfer of water from soil to the above part of the plants 	<p>Root-knots on tomato roots</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop rotation • Using resistant varieties • Fallow plowing • Digging the soil during hot season
6. Blossom-end rot	It is physiological disorder caused by deficiency of calcium in the distal end of the fruit. Fluctuation in water supply favors the disease occurrence.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Light tan, water soaked lesions, which turn to black and leathery at the blossom end of the fruit. Affected fruits ripen more rapidly than the normal once. 	<p>Blossom-end rot on tomato fruits</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper fertilization and water management • Foliar spraying of calcium-based fertilizer

<p>7. Sunscald</p>	<p>Occurred when fruits exposed to high temperatures (40 °C and above) and high sunlight. Varieties having sparse foliage, thin pericarp and immature size are more prone to sunscald.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whitish, greyish, sunken and papery lesions on fruits • Lesions can be entry point for secondary infection resulting black dark spots that make fruits unfit for consumption 	<p>Sunscalding on tomato fruit</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoiding unnecessary pruning of branches and exposing fruits to direct sunlight • Tying the leaves to cover the fruits • Using varieties resistant to the foliage diseases
<p>8. Blotchy ripening</p>	<p>Physiological disorder caused mainly by Potassium (K) deficiency. Occurs due to an imbalance of N and K (high levels of N, Ca and Na).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Causes uneven ripening and reduces fruit quality • Greenish-yellow to whitish patch on tomato fruits, mostly on the stem-end portion of the fruits 	<p>Uneven ripening of tomato fruit</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applying a fertilizer that contains potassium nutrient

6. HARVESTING, YIELD AND POSTHARVEST HANDLING OF TOMATOES

6.1. Harvesting

Tomatoes grown in protected structure including in low-cost plastic house are mostly hand harvested using hand tools. Tomato can be harvested at different stages depending the time required to reach the market place (distance to market place). For long distance transport, tomatoes should be harvested at early maturity stages like breaker and turning stages (Fig. 14). Fruit for local market are harvested at later ripening stages. Harvesting during cool periods, such as late in the afternoon or early in the morning is recommended. The harvested fruits should be placed in holding containers (plastics or buckets), which are free of rough edges to reduce damages. Avoid any damages during harvesting. Harvested fruits should be carefully handled. Inappropriate handling leads to fruit injury/damages and poor quality and increased postharvest losses.

Stage	Color	Description
1	Green	The surface is completely green in color. The shade of green may vary from light to dark.
2	Breakers	There is a definite "break" in color from green to tarnish-yellow, pink or red on less than 10% of the surface.
3	Turning	10% to 30% of the surface shows a change in color from green to tarnish-yellow, pink, red or a combination thereof.
4	Pink	30% to 60% of the surface shows pink or red in color.
5	Light Red	60% to 90% of the surface shows pinkish-red or red.
6	Red	More than 90% of the surface is red.

Fig. 14: Maturity stages of tomatoes

Source: Elhariri et al. (2014)

6.2. Yield of Tomatoes

The productivity of tomatoes depends on the type of variety, environmental conditions, management practices and the production system. The yield of tomatoes under protected structure including low-cost plastic house is much higher compared to open field production system. Moreover, hybrid tomato varieties have high yielding potential compared to open pollinated varieties. In this regard, Getahun (2019) reported that Melkashola and Melkasalsa, both open pollinated varieties of tomato, in low-cost plastic house production system recorded the marketable yield of 37.6 and 38.7 t ha⁻¹, respectively, in Fogera district of Amhara Region. Similarly, Alemayehu and Alemayehu (2017) stated that Roma VF, an open-pollinated variety of tomato produced the fruit yield of 31.4 t ha⁻¹ under rain shelter technology. Tegegne et al. (2021) also reported the mean marketable fruit yields of 25.5 and 24.7 t ha⁻¹ from Melkashola and Melkasalsa varieties (open pollinated) of tomatoes, respectively, in low-cost plastic shelter under farmers practices. They also reported that growing Melkasala and Melkashola varieties under rain shelter increased the marketable yield by 114.5% and 98.4%, respectively, compared to their productivity in open field production system during the rainy season.

On the other hand, in the research conducted under low-cost plastic house constructed on four different farmer`s land at Koga Irrigation Scheme, the hybrid tomato varieties Galilea, Gabi and Galilea-39 across four locations recorded the average marketable fruit yields of 82.6, 89.1, 83.7 t ha⁻¹, respectively (Abebu, 2024). Generally, the yield performance of hybrid tomato varieties under low-cost plastic house is much higher than the open-pollinated varieties. The use these varieties in protected structure during the rainy season contribute for the continuous supply of the market with fresh tomatoes and enhancement of the income and livelihood of the smallholder farmers in Ethiopia.

6.3. Postharvest Handling

The harvested fruits should be collected into holding containers (plastic or wooden crates) placed under shade in the farm. Exposing harvested fruit to temperatures above 25 °C reduces the shelf life and increases postharvest losses. Sorting should be practiced after harvesting where bruised and insect pest-, as well as disease-damaged fruits are removed and disposed properly. Plant debris in the farm should be also removed and disposed properly as they can be an inoculum source for the next production season.

Grading increases the values of tomato fruits. Tomatoes are graded depending on the uniformity of ripening and fruit size. While big-sized fruits of uniform color and shape are graded as Grade 1, medium-sized fruits are graded as Grade 2. Small-sized fruits with slight variation in color and shape are graded as Grade 3.

It is advisable to transport tomatoes using wooden-, or plastic crates that are free of any rough edges to avoid damages on the fruits. The transport of tomatoes from farm to the market should be done early in the morning when temperature is relatively low to reduce losses. Animal-draft for small quantity and motor vehicles for relatively large quantity are used for the transportation of tomatoes to the market place.

Due to its perishable nature of the crop, fresh tomatoes cannot be stored for a long period of time like potatoes. If storage is indispensable, it can be stored in cold storage at 7-13 °C and 85-95% relative humidity, depending of the maturity stages. Such a cold storage however requires relatively high investment costs and electricity, which is not affordable for smallholder farmers.

Zero energy cooling chamber (ZECC), which is introduced from India can be used to store tomatoes at farmer`s as well as trader`s level. The ZECC is constructed using locally available materials like double-walled bricks. The roof is made of wood and grass (Fig. 15). The 15 cm cavity between the two bricks-walls is filled with riverbed sand, which should be watered daily. The investment cost is relatively small. The temperature in ZECC can be maintained by about 5-10 °C less than the outside temperature and the relative humidity greater than 80% depending on the outside environment.

Fig. 15: Zero Energy Cooling Chamber for tomato storage

Source: Ethio-SHEP (2019)

7. COST AND INCOME ANALYSIS OF TOMATO PRODUCTION

Record keeping is very important for evaluating the profitability of a given farm including tomato production. Therefore, the farmers are encouraged to keep accurate records of all farm activities that incur costs. The record should include both the cost of production and sales so that the farmers are able to analyze whether tomato-farming makes profit or loss.

The life span of the low-cost plastic house is assumed to be three years. Therefore, yearly cost of the house can be calculated by dividing the total investment cost of the house to three years.

A simplified sample sheet is presented below (Table 3) that helps recording the gross income, production and sale costs and the gross benefit of tomato farming under low-cost plastic house.

Table 3: Major items and activities to be considered for determining gross margin of tomato production

Item	Quantity	Unit price	Total	Remark
A. Yearly cost of low-cost plastic house				Total cost/3
B. Input costs				
Seed				
Manure/compost				
Fertilizer				
Staking wood				
Chemicals				
C. Costs for land preparation				
D. Labor cost for planting				
E. Management costs				
Cultivation				
Watering and fertilizer application				
Harvesting				
F. Transportation and packaging cost				
G. Total cost (A+B+C+D+E+F)				
H. Marketable yield				Gross income
I. Net income (H-G)				

Reference

- Abebu, Z. (2024). Growth and yield performance of hybrid tomato (*Lycopersicon esculuntem* Mill) varieties under polyhouse during rainy season at Koga Irrigation Scheme, Northwest, Ethiopia. M.Sc. Thesis, Bahir Dar University, Ethiopia, pp. 104.
- Alemayehu, M. and Alemayehu, G. (2017). Study on alternative technologies for the production of tomato during the rainy season in sub-humid climate of Bahir Dar, Ethiopia. *Ethiop. J. Sci. & Technol.* 10(1): 1-16. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/ejst.v10i1.1>
- Elhariri, E., El-Bendary, N., Hassaniien, A.E., Badr, A., Hussein, A.M.M., and Sn'asel, V. (2014). Random Forests Based Classification for Crops Ripeness Stages. In: P. Krömer et al. (eds.), *Proceedings of the Fifth Intern. Conf. on Innov. in Bio-Inspired Comput. and Appl. IBICA 2014*, Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing 303, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-08156-4_21, Springer International Publishing Switzerland 2014
- Ethio-SHEP, (2019). Tomato Production. The Project for Smallholder Horticulture Farmer Empowerment through Promotion of Market-Oriented Agriculture, JICA and MoA, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. [02_08_01_04.pdf \(jica.go.jp\)](http://www.jica.go.jp/02_08_01_04.pdf)
- Getahun, D. (2019). Responses of Tomato Varieties to Rainy Season Production under Low Cost Plastic Shelter. *International Journal of Research Studies in Agricultural Sciences*, 5(2): 1-6
- Lin, L-J., Luther, G.C., Hanson, P. (2015). Raising healthy tomato seedlings. AVRDC – The World Vegetable Center publication #15-795. 15 p.
- Tegegne, M.A. Melaku, E., Ayichew, S. (2021). Economic feasibility of plastic shelter tomato production method under rain-fed in Fogera plain, North Western Ethiopia. *Int. J. Adv. Res. Biol. Sci.* 8(12): 142-147